

EFFECTIVE USE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN PROVIDING THE MENTAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8271736>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 14th August 2023

Accepted: 21th August 2023

Online: 22th August 2023

KEY WORDS

Preschool age, education, teacher (educator), child, mental activity, didactics, thinking, preschool education organization.

ABSTRACT

The game is the main activity of preschool children, through which the child is formed as a person. The game determines the degree to which the child's future education, work, and attitude towards people will be formed. The game appears as an important means of education.

The great Russian pedagogue K. D. Ushinsky comments that "when the education given to children is conducted based on the didactic principle, their spiritual development is particularly effective." He created a wonderful work called "Children's World" Mother Tongue to teach children about life objects and events around them. Didactic principles are derived from basic didactic rules implemented in preschool education organization.

Didactics (theory of education: the Greek "didaktikos" means "teacher", and "didasko" means "to teach") theoretical aspects of education (the essence, principles, laws of the educational process, the field that studies the content of teacher (educator) and student (educated) activity, educational goal, form, method, means, result, ways to improve the educational process, and other problems).

This word was introduced in Germany in 1613 by the German pedagogue Wolfgang Rathke (1571-1635). The great Czech pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius (1592-1670) mentions this concept in a similar way in his famous work "The Great Didactic". But Comensky emphasizes that "didactics is not only education, but also education." In this work, the scientist talks about the important issues of the theory of education: the content of education, the principles of demonstration and sequence of education, and the training system.

"Didactics" is a set of toys that help children's mental and sensory education.

The game is the main activity of preschool children, through which the child is formed as a person. The game determines the degree to which the child's future education, work, and attitude towards people will be formed. The game appears as an important means of education.

The demands and needs of a young organism in the game is satisfied. Vital activity is created. Unity, freshness, cheerfulness are cultivated. Games and activities are closely related to observations in everyday life and have great educational value. Interest in learning what is

reflected in the game is aroused, often the game serves to give children new knowledge and expand their thoughts and knowledge. Children's games are distinguished by their variety. They differ according to their content and organization, according to the types of materials used, according to their origin.

In pedagogy, it is very common to divide games into two large groups: creative games and games with rules. Children themselves come up with the content of creative games and reflect their impressions, understanding of existence and their relationship to it. Games with rules are created by adults and brought into the life of a child. The group of creative games consists of role-playing games with a plot. Games are conditionally divided into didactic games and musical games according to their content and rules, educational effect.

In didactic games, first of all, children's mental activity develops, their knowledge deepens and expands, in movement games, children's various actions are improved, and in musical games, musical abilities are developed. So, each game has its own qualities, but they also have a number of common features.

In preschool educational organizations, games start in the morning before breakfast (15-20 minutes) and are held after breakfast, between classes, in the open air, after sleep. In the morning, it is recommended to organize role-playing games, construction and action games, and action games with rules are also held in the middle of the training. Outdoor games include games related to running, shooting, sliding, and games with rules. Games after daytime sleep include construction games, role-playing games, and didactic games based on fairy tales.

Education of children of preschool age is a process of formation of knowledge and skills in them, in which the educator sets certain tasks for the children, and they get the correct understanding of the world around them. He explains them in the simplest way through things and events. The game teaches them to use the knowledge and skills acquired in the game. Education requires adherence to didactic principles. Didactic games are widely used as an educational tool in preschool educational organizations.

The didactic game is directly related to education and helps it, didactic is a methodical experience of teaching that matches the age and capabilities of preschool children, the teacher mixes passive children into a team in this game and performs various plans and tasks. used to perform without fear.

The didactic game should be in accordance with the task and goals of education. A didactic game helps children to form good relationships, such as combining their interests with the interests of the team, helping each other and being happy about the success of their friends. It allows the formation of positive feelings such as "ylik".

Didactic games for children are held for the following purposes: Organization of team games to develop the skill of playing didactic riddles in children; sorting things by only one color sorting them by big and small sorting adults and cubes in a regular form playing games based on two quadrilateral, hexagonal cross-section pictures depicting objects and so on.

Didactic games in the classes aim to solve the following tasks: observation, the ability to check things, compare them with each other, the ability to notice small differences in their signs, color, shape, size, material, and tell the changes in the location of things. education of sensory skills such as picking, being able to find their names when describing and classifying animals, plants, vehicles, developing skills, developing children's general imagination, the

ability to group objects according to common signs, and filling in parts from good things is to develop skills to play with.

The existence of the life situation in didactic games increases the child's thinking and improves the content of the plot and role-playing games. In the game, the child's experience of movement is formed. Didactic games, as an educational game, belong to the group of games suitable for the age characteristics of children.

An important feature of didactic games is the presence of rules in it. In the game, there is an integral connection between the board, the rules of the game, and the actions of the game. The board of the game determines the nature of the actions. The rules of the game help to solve the game's actions and tasks and perform the actions in the game. Children are given new knowledge and concepts through didactic games. These games improve children's all-round development, knowledge process, sensory culture, speech culture, and mental abilities. Observing the rules of the game and following them enriches the content of the game.

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